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“THE OFW”

Luisa stared at her sleeping five-year-old son. Teary-eyed, she kissed her goodbye. She’s leaving again to work abroad. After ending her contract in the United Arab Emirates, she’s flying away from home again to Singapore, after a six-month rest. It was never an easy decision but she has to, in order to give her family a better future. She then gave her husband a hug, and waved goodbye, as she said, “I’ll be home in three years.”

Luisa’s life has never been easy. With her three children, the fifteen-year-old, Alana, ten-year-old, Maria, and the five-year-old, Lucas, she knew she had to grind even more in order to give them a better future. Her husband, Juancho, used to be a taxi driver but considering the expenses now, and the price of goods, not to mention the incredibly increasing cost of living, she knew she had to step up.

In Singapore, she will be working as a nanny to a seven-year-old little girl. Before she even signed the contract, she made sure she’d get well acquainted with Singapore’s culture and language. She figured; she’ll need this in order to connect and communicate to them better.

As soon as her new employers welcomed her into their home, she made sure that they will be getting along well with each other. She knew beforehand that Singaporean people are strict when it comes to cleanliness, thus, she made sure that the house is always clean, especially Zeta’s room. Zeta, is the little girl she had to look after. Luisa also knew she had to be a wise and caring nanny to Zeta, thus, she also makes sure Zeta is always safe with her. She treats her as her own. Luisa also figured the difference between Singapore’s way of living from that of the UAE. This made her decide to take big efforts in adjusting from having a fast-paced living in UAE to a more structured and highly efficient environment in Singapore. Luisa, however, is glad she is a Filipino since we have a culture of being hospitable and being able to get along well with people. These cultures helped Luisa so much in adjusting to this new kind of environment.

One day, her employers asked her to run some errands. Since her employer had a fever, she needs to do the shopping for her. At first, Luisa hesitated because this will be the first time she will be walking outside the house alone. But she took courage. With a smartphone in her hand, she asked the help of the google map to go to the supermarket. She carefully memorized her employer’s instructions as well as the directions. Gladly, she accomplished the task successfully.

On her way home, as she rode the train, she suddenly felt her stomach grumble. She feels a little hungry. She was about to grab a bite of the cracker she had brought earlier when she remembered one of Singapore’s most important cultures, to avoid eating or drinking in a public transport. So, in order to show respect to the Singaporean culture, she put the cracker down and waited until she took off the train.

Luisa knew that there are many things she has to learn in this place and, she is confident enough that she will be able to work her best in it. After all, she is a Filipino, and Filipino's are among the most known people in the world to be warm, flexible, hospitable, and vibrant.

